

THE PURPOSE OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN NON-SPECIALIZED HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: One of the pressing issues of the current era is the upbringing of the younger generation through the teaching of foreign languages in the spirit of love and loyalty to the motherland, national pride, high morality and spirituality, a sense of pride to our ancient and rich heritage, national and universal values.

Keywords: non-philological educational institutions, international standards, linguistic information, extra linguistic information.

Fundamental reforms in the world education system are advancing the problems of creating the necessary conditions for students to learn foreign languages perfectly, to be able to manifest themselves in all areas with knowledge of a foreign language, to develop their oral and written speech in a foreign language. Organizations such as UNESCO, UNICEF, European University Association, European Network for the quality of higher education are engaged in issues of thinking in a foreign language, developing the ability to carry out free speaking skills, formation of intellectual activity, assessment of their readiness. The development of this issue in general trends to great importance in modernity and the formation of foreign language skills in teaching the younger generation, serving to increase the creative abilities of students in connection with the problems of modern upbringing.

In the reform of the educational system of our republic, coordination with educational programs corresponding to international standards based on foreign experiences became the basis for improving the higher pedagogical educational system. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, a radical reform of the quality of education on the basis of foreign experiences, taking into account our national mentality, traditions, is a requirement of the period.

Special attention is also paid to the teaching of foreign languages thanks to independence in our country. The fact that thousands of foreign language teachers have been prepared, all conditions have been created for the qualification of personnel in our native country and abroad, multimedia textbooks on English, German, French, electronic resources for learning English have been prepared, modern equipped rooms have been established in educational institutions. On the basis of improving the education of the younger generation in foreign languages and the training of specialists who can speak these languages fluently, the main goal was to create conditions for the achievements of the World Youth and the use of information resources from all over the world, the development of international cooperation and dialogue. Famous German scientist Goethe said: "Whoever does not know foreign languages does not even know his own language". For this reason, not only foreign language specialists, but also all future personnel studying in higher educational institutions that do not specialize in the language, being able to study foreign languages and exchange ideas freely in them is considered one of the most important tasks. One of the main requirements for personnel today is excellent knowledge of foreign languages.

In the processes of training specialists in all areas, it is important to ensure the priority of the educational system, including the introduction of new technology - mechanisms for teaching foreign languages. After all, communication between peoples, spiritual and other dialogues are manifested through language.

The world is conducting research on teaching foreign languages to students of higher educational institutions that do not specialize in languages in the following priority areas: improving pedagogical mechanisms for teaching foreign languages to students on the basis of Universal CEFR requirements; strengthening the objectivity of teaching content, educational technologies, control, organizing independent education in addition to audience.

The goals of teaching a foreign language are determined based on the demand, social order, circumstances, policy of society. The goals of teaching a foreign language depend on the development of society. Teaching a foreign language in higher educational institutions has own goals, all coaches who teach a foreign language are sure to clarify it in advance.

Taking into account the goals and objectives of teaching English in higher education institutions, they can be divided into 2 groups:

1. Foreign Language-University, Institute, faculties that train specialists in English.
2. Foreign language-non-philological educational institutions that do not prepare an English specialist.

In these 2 groups, the goals of teaching English are different, and due to the preparation of a specialist in English in higher education institutions of the first group, English is taught in a deep all-round perfect, both theoretical and practical. In the second group, i.e., non-philological educational institutions, a comprehensive English language goal is envisaged. The goal lies in teaching the student to take a general education from English and again apply English in his specialty in the future in his work activities. Partial communication by profession is taught to read and translate texts, studying words related to their specialty.

In conclusion, teaching a foreign language in higher educational institutions that do not specialize in languages is necessary because a foreign language is of great importance for preparing students for comprehensive maturity.

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